

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Farmers experiences and interest to use different methods to improve soil quality

Farmers perceptions of soil quality are of high importance in the development of more sustainable farming practices. The farmer survey implemented in SoildiverAgro identified relevant soil related agri-environmental problems in the present production as well as the most effective farming practices to face these problems. The survey data was collected from six different regions of Europe. In Finland 357 farmers provided survey answers. Of them 71 % were conventional farmers and 29% organic. With a survey measure we aimed to understand farmers current and prospective adoption of soil management practices on their farms. In Finland among the 13 practices

assessed, the most popular was less frequent ploughing and reducing tillage depth. over 70% of farmers expressed interest in them. Also implementing long rotation periods in cultivation was interesting as 70% intended to apply it in future. We also measured farmers perceptions of the possible impacts of different practices. Especially covering field with organic matter, intercropping and cover crops were seen as practices that contribute to good soil quality. The overall attitude towards improving soil quality was rather positive in Finland 4,1 on the scale from one to five. Still, it was lower than in other countries of the study.

1. In Finland, farmers generally consider the soil quality on their fields to be rather good

KEYWORDS

Interest to apply, soil management, farmers intentions

AUTHORSHIP

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